

Economic Crisis and Poverty in Nigeria: the Private Sector and Market Forces to the Rescue?

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ABSTRACT

The current global economic crisis is primarily occasioned by the cumulative effects of the COVID19 pandemic, the Russia-Ukraine war, emerging US/China trade hostilities, and the deepening environmental effects of climate change. As advocated by Western institutions, the impetus for economic growth is a liberalized private sector-driven economy, determined by market forces. The Nigerian state is severely impacted by the prevailing economic crunch despite its entrenched neo-liberalize economic system. Hence, the paper aims to examine the viability of Nigeria neoliberal orthodoxy in the current economic crisis. The research is anchored on the Keynesian model to explain and predict the variables of the study. The descriptive-analytical technique involving content analysis of secondary data was employed. Findings revealed that the floating exchange rate, fuel subsidy removal without adequate cushioning measures amongst others, are tailored along the market-rational systems approach, which the paper argued is counter-productive to timely economic revival. Therefore, what is required is effective government intervention by firstly; reconsidering its fiscal and monetary policies to stabilize the Naira; engage in massive productive spending on infrastructure and industrialization; incentivize the non-formal sector and local entrepreneurs to grow businesses, which will generate economies of scale and multipliers for the economy; develop a productive public/private sector synergy in scientific innovation and technological development; initiate effective policy measures to spur foreign and domestic investment; embark on inclusive economic empowerment programmes for growth and poverty reduction and; tackle the malaise of corruption, counteracting the nation's drive for economic recovery.

Keywords: Economic Crisis, Private Sector, Market Forces, Growth, Development

1. INTRODUCTION

The measuring yardstick of a democratic government is the extent of its stride towards safeguarding civil liberty, guarantee security and ensure socio-economic wellbeing of the people within its sphere of territorial authority. In Nigeria, this contractual imperative of government is elusive rather, what obtains is the crisis of insecurity, and a gloomy economic outlook. The nation's current economic crisis is argued to emanate from the prevailing global economic crunch. But more significantly are internal economic contradictions due to poor governance, poor policy implementation, and mismanagement of the nation's resources (UN-OCHA, 2024; AFDB/AFDF, 2024). The economy is bedeviled with fiscal and monetary policy crisis, poor productivity level in the mineral and industrial sector, high foreign exchange, high inflationary trend, and depreciation of the Naira. Other economic challenges include debt crisis, deficit funding, energy crisis arising from subsidy removal, with consequences for cost of doing business. There is notably high production and transportation cost, high cost of goods

and services, high cost of living, overall decline in foreign and domestic investment, lack of competitive capacity in foreign trade relations, overreliance on imports, as well as sustained unemployment and job losses (Farayibi, 2016; EU, 2023).

The Nigerian state is besieged with existential poverty crisis due to the current economic crunch, as most households lack access to basic needs for their daily survival. There is growing mass hunger resulting from unemployment and lack of financial resources for commercial engagement. Accrued income of those engaged in the formal and non-formal economic sector is below the acceptable survivability threshold; their plight is further worsened by the eroded value of the Naira due to inflation. The impact of the economic crisis on business performance is also very visible. Businesses continue to decline due to the difficulty of sustainability as Naira continues to depreciate, with high exchange rate and poor disposable income of consumers. Struggling businesses to stay afloat are either compelled to downsize staff strength or slashed workers' salaries. The nation's dysfunctional socioeconomic trajectory is also evident in the absence of critical public utilities. Many Nigerian parents and guardians have been forced to withdraw their wards from the school system due to high cost of fees. There is inadequate educational infrastructure; and the masses lack the economic ability to access the few functional institutions. More so, economic crisis and poverty have taken its toll on the people's ability to access the grossly inadequate public health care system in Nigeria (Bilquin & Delivorias, 2023; NESG Repot 2023).

Due to economic deprivation and quest for survival, there is rising incidence of banditry, kidnapping for ransom, extortion and armed robbery, which has dislocated the social and economic fabrics of the nation. There is also the preponderance of cybercrimes, petty stealing, fraudulent schemes, and financial crimes. Others are street hawking, child trafficking, and prostitution. This climate of insecurity presents a serious disincentive for investment opportunities and job creation. Consequently, scarce resources expected to be deployed in stimulating the economy and accelerate economic growth is deployed to fighting the nation's insecurity (Nigeria Bureau of Statistic, 2023; NESG Repot 2023).

In the light of the overwhelming socio-economic challenges confronting the nation, the factor of leadership becomes critical. It is observed that the incipient government of President Tinubu - the 'Renewed Hope' agenda, has continues to evolve economic policies to address the hydra-headed economic crisis in the country, especially in the monetary and fiscal components of the economy. Key among these policies are the floating exchange rate, the fuel subsidy removal, lifting ban on foreign importations amongst others, which many consider as neo-liberal economic measures, which emphasizes the private sector and the market-rational systems, and which the paper argued as counter-productive to timely economic revival. But the question is, can the private sector-led economy and reliance on the market forces, be the ultimate economic mechanism in savaging the current economic crisis confronting the nation? The objective of this paper therefore, is to examine the viability of Nigeria neoliberal orthodoxy in the current economic crisis, in the quest for economic recovery and stability. The rest of the paper is organized as follows: Following section one which is introduction, section two is devoted to literature review, section three explores economic crisis and poverty in Nigeria, while section four is on assessment of the economic policy of government, section five concludes the paper.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

The Private Sector Economy and Market Forces

The neoliberal or the private sector based economy is overwhelmingly advocated as a catalyst for speeding economic process of growth due to its ability to catalyze product competitiveness and efficiency. To neo-liberalists, the privates sector is driven by profit motive. The profit motive drives innovators to create new ideas. The profit motive drives entrepreneurs to place new inventions into production; the profit motive drives investors to build the factories required by the entrepreneur. Furthermore, the profit motive drives other inventors, entrepreneur, and investors to offer competitive products, thereby raising the quality of the product and reduces its price (Mazzucato & Mariana, 2015). Thus, as profit multiplies, investors seek an ever-expanding wave of projects in which to invest their money, and the outcome is rapid economic growth. Consequently, the ensuing economic growth provides jobs and improves wellbeing. In line with this argument, the classical laissez-faire contends that so many third world countries are falling farther behind the states of the first world because politicians regulate the free market, thereby reducing its effectiveness (Koyama & Jared, 2022).

Hence, strict adherence to the economic principles of the ‘Washington Consensus’ centered on neoliberal advocacies becomes a prerequisite for foreign assistance by Pro-Western financial institutions like the International Monetary Fund (IMF) and World Bank. The key reason for advancing an open market economy by International Financial Institutions (IFI) is the claim that reliance on market forces will correct the perceived distortion in the economy like import substitution, market regulation, over-valuation of the naira required to be adjusted via devaluation etc. which are considered inimical to growth (Lin, 2014).

However, many economist and leaders in the third world reject the assumption of a self-regulating market. They are of the view that while capitalist in orientation, the state must supplement market forces. They believe that the market must be regulated as capitalists do not always act like capitalists. The potentially destructive competition for markets often give way to cartels and other “deals” designed to share profits and reduce competition. Conversely, one area of the market may be so dominated by a particular firm that a monopoly exists. New products are prevented from entering the market and productivity stagnates (De Loecker, Eeckhout, & Unger, 2020). It is observed that, reliance on market forces has not significantly benefited developing economy because the system has not encouraged efficient allocation of resources for the overall development of the countries’ economic sectors; rather it has resulted in de-industrialization and trade deficit (Acemoglu, 2023).

The arguments on economic ideologies have subsisted regarding the extent of government involvement in the economy and organizing and directing the market towards economic development, as there are records of successes and failures among nations who have engaged these ideas in driving their economies with varying successes and failures. The remarkable successes of the United States and China; the two greatest economic superpower nations, with deferential economic ideologies will have continued to reinforce these ideological arguments. But as observed in Nigeria, despite the adoption of a more open private sector economy beginning with the privatization of State Own Enterprise (SOE), pre-existing contradictions of economic crisis still prevails leading to sustained unemployment and chronic poverty, high prices of basic commodities, as well as falling public expenditures on health and education with increasing infrastructural decay. This work therefore aims to interrogate the private sector economy and unravel its typical characteristics as it applies to economic growth and

development, employment issues, social welfare, equality and higher standard of living in Nigeria.

The Keynesian Theoretical Perspective on Economic Growth

The Keynesian perspective centers on government spending to revive the economy (also referred to as aggregate demand), and its effect on output and inflation. The Keynesian model believes that aggregate demand is influenced by a host of economic decisions, both public and private which sometimes behaves erratically. The public decisions include, most prominently, those on monetary and fiscal (i.e. spending and tax) policies (Keynes, 1936). According to Keynesian theory, changes in aggregate demand, whether anticipated or unanticipated, have their greatest short-run effect on real output and employment. Thus his emphasis of economic change is the short effect, because in his view, we live in the short run. His proponents often quote his famous statement, “In the long run, we are all dead,” to make the point (Mankiw, 1993). Suffice to say that in a critical economic circumstance, what is required in the short-run is immediate public intervention via massive government spending.

According to Blinder (1986), some Keynesians are more concerned about combating unemployment than about conquering inflation. They have concluded from the evidence that the costs of low inflation are small. However, views on the relative importance of unemployment and inflation heavily influence the policy advice that economists give and that policymakers accept. Keynesians typically advocate more aggressively expansionist policies than non-Keynesians. Thus the emphasis is that government should intervene in the economy monetarily to shore up public spending and benefit from the multipliers for economic growth, especially during recession or economic downturn. Keynesians’ belief in aggressive government action in relations to public spending to stabilize the economy is based on value judgments and on the beliefs that (a) macroeconomic fluctuations significantly reduce economic well-being and (b) the government is knowledgeable and capable enough to improve on the free market.

If government spending increases, for example, and all other components of spending remain constant, then output will increase. In the Keynesian models of economic activity, the multiplier effect is the output increases by a multiple of the original change in spending that caused it. Thus, a ten-billion-dollar increase in government spending could cause total output to rise by fifteen billion dollars (a multiplier of 1.5) or by five billion (a multiplier of 0.5) (Keynes, 1936). However, they argue that monetary policy can produce real effects on output and employment only if some prices are rigid, if nominal wages (wages in dollars, not in real purchasing power), for example, do not adjust instantly. Otherwise, an injection of new money would change all prices by the same percentage. So Keynesian models generally either assume or try to explain rigid prices or wages (Keynes 1936; Blinder, 1986).

In the Nigerian context, the imperative of government intervention is to formulate effective regulatory policies to guarantee a level playing ground for businesses to thrive, and sound economic policies to grow the economy, create jobs, build infrastructure and develop the industrial sector. These policies may include limited public spending due to lack of financial capital in the country. Greater percentage of public revenue generated is directed towards debt servicing. In attempt to boost its financial resources, government embarked on neoliberal policies like subsidy removal which has further placed the masses in a precarious situation. It can also be argued that economic policies that are insensitive to the plight of the masses with sole focus on the big players in the private sector will amount to cartelization and cannot be

termed a responsible approach.

3. ECONOMIC CRISIS AND POVERTY IN NIGERIA: THE PRIVATE SECTOR AND MARKET FORCES TO THE RESCUE?

This segment attempts to provide assessment of economic viability of the private sector economy as it relates to economic recovery and development. Based on the 2014 economic rebasing exercise under a private sector driven economy, Nigeria attained a milestone of being the largest economy in Africa (Nigeria Bureau of Statistics, 2014). However, the impact of this growth on the socioeconomic development is a subject of contention. Under a private sector economy, the poverty situation amongst Nigerians continues to worsen. National Bureau of Statistics figures released 2015 show that poverty level was increasing at the same time that the overall economic growth rate was being reported. Nigeria in 2013 was ranked around 160th out of 177 countries on the scale of the Human Development Index (HDI). Large majority of the population experience extremely limited access to services such as schools and health centers, and about half of the population lacks access to safe drinking water. It is therefore evident that the country is unable to translate its apparent high economic growth rate into poverty reduction (<http://www.poverties.org/poverty-in-nigeria.html>, 2013; CDD, 2013; NBS, 2015). More so, when poverty is measured in terms of people living below \$1.25 per day, about 67.98% of Nigerians were living below the poverty line when we have just 13.77%. The poverty rate in over half of Nigeria 36 states is over the national average of 69%. High poverty reflects rising unemployment, estimated at 23.1% in 2018, up from 14% in 2016. Low skill limits opportunity for employment in the formal private sector economy. Government social programs – N-power and other youth empowerment schemes have not been able to address the unemployment challenges (World Bank Report - Nigeria Economic Outlook, 2020).

Nigerians do not have access to basic services, specifically access to shelter, clean Water, sanitation and hygiene (UN- NCCA (2022)). According to the World Bank Nigeria Development Update-NDU (2023), about 133 million Nigerians are currently living below the poverty line. The soaring inflationary pressure in 2023, added 4 million Nigerians to the existing number of people living within the poverty bracket (NESG, 2023). The Nigeria's health sector is abysmal. Maternal and child health remain poor, due to weak health systems and socioeconomic factors. Nigeria is still challenged by out-of-school children. The number of out-of-school children was estimated to have increased from 10.5 million to 13.2 million as at 2018, with the conflict in the North East a major factor (<https://documents1.worldbank.org>).

It is estimated that about 26.5 million Nigerians will grapple with acute food insecurity, and about 9 million children stand the risk of suffering from acute malnutrition or death. Of these figure, 2.6 million children could face Severe Acute Malnutrition (SAM) and require critical nutrition treatment. The projection for 2024 indicates a remarkable increase of 18.6 million people who were vulnerable to food insecurity from October to December 2023. This situation is attributed to a combination of factors namely; the effects of climate change, global conflicts, escalating inflationary trend, and rising costs of both food and essential non-food commodities; partly due to the devaluation of the naira and discontinuation of the fuel subsidy. Other factors include the persistent violence in the north-eastern states of Borno, Adamawa, and Yobe, which pose serious challenge to food access and availability. Armed banditry and kidnappings in northwest and north-central states, including Katsina, Sokoto, Kaduna, Benue, and Niger, is equally a factor in the worsening economic crisis ravaging the nation (ReliefWeb, 2024: IPCINFO, 2023).

Benchmarking the Private Sector and Market Forces as Catalyst for Economic Recovery and Development

To ascertain the economic viability of the private sector economy regulated by market forces, attempt will be made to examine its effect on key variables bordering social justices and socioeconomic wellbeing of Nigerians. They include; social safety/protection for vulnerable group, provision of basic economic infrastructure, human right concerns, social responsibilities, and socio-economic equality, as well as job creation/employment.

Social Safety/Protection for Vulnerable Group

Social protection ensures equity and justice regarding availability of equal socioeconomic opportunities for all as relates to basic needs and social welfare, and that vulnerable and minority groups are equally accommodated in government policies and programmes. However, the operational context of private sector economy in Nigeria does not guarantee that government is aligned with the vulnerable groups namely; the poor, women, aged, etc in terms of protecting and/or expanding their access to basic social and infrastructural services (Ejitu & Okechuwkwu, 2023). The implication of this is deprivation of ordinary people, who find it difficult to cope with provocative costs as the private sector aims to maximize profit. Thus operations of private sector economy, raises the question of accountability to whom, the people, or to the markets?

Provision of Basic Economic Infrastructure

Economic growth and development is anchored on existing industrial base which is impossible without adequate infrastructure capacity that will provide the impetus for conversion of available material resources into an increased aggregate output and flourishing economy. However, the private sector led economy in Nigeria has not reproduced the phenomenal infrastructural stride that characterized the pre-privatization era of the 60s. The interventionist effort of the federal government in the areas of roads, rail, strategic bridges, water supply and sewages, steel plants, electricity, petrochemical complexes, adequate schools and well equipped health centers, has dwindled following the handing over of the economy to the private sector. There is a severe infrastructural deficit in Nigeria, which pose a threat to national wellbeing and development (Ogunde, 2001; Olamide, 2018). Post privatization contradiction is evident in the crisis of electricity supply, fuel scarcity, unreliable healthcare services, unstable educational institutions, bad roads, malfunctioning ports, exorbitant telecommunication services, and lack of pipe borne water. It can be argued that, it is the poor performance of private sector that impacted government's unwillingness to privatize the comatose refineries, preferring to import fuel from abroad.

Human Right Concerns, Social Responsibilities, and Socio-Economic Equality

The international human rights instrument of which Nigeria is obliged, in line with its principles of state policy requires the "control of the national economy in such a manner as to secure the maximum welfare, freedom and happiness of every citizen on the basis of social justice and equality of status and opportunity" (The Nigerian Constitution, 1999). It envisages the management of the economy in a way that impacts on the greater majority of the people through distribution of goods and services. A human right approach to development would require equity in production and distribution, and must emphasize a major expansion of basic social services to reach all the deprived population. It also involves the removal of barriers to the entry of people in economic and political sphere and the equalization of their access to opportunities (Ejitu and Okechuwkwu, 2023). The private sector economy may spur growth but does not look promising regarding poverty reduction and economic and social empowerment of the

poor. There is the strong argument that a private sector economy has led to the concentration of factors of production in the hands of a particular group towards the exploitation of the nation resources. In this regards, the burden lies on the government to focus on human welfare, equitable-distribution and investment in the provision of social goods to cushion the harsh impact of a private sector economy.

Job Creation/Employment

Job availability provides the means by which people can earn and make a living, thus it is a very important criterion in determining the extent of growth inclusiveness. Government is responsible for promoting both the formal and informal economic sector to fully engage the masses and catalyze growth. Job opportunity provide incomes to household, in generating resources to be invested in children's education and health, in raising economic productivity, and in providing a sense of social wellbeing (World Bank Development Report, 2013). Job opportunity has been shown to lift the masses out of poverty in developing economies. However, in a private sector driven economy, business firms are absolutely profit driven, and such workers are seen as ready tool to be engaged when the condition are favorable and thrown out when the conditions are not.

Records have shown that Nigeria fared better in job creation between 1991 and 1999, before the privatization exercise that consolidated the private sector economy in Nigeria. Within this period, unemployment rate was less than 5%, however, unemployment rate rose consistently between 1999 and 2013 to about 23.9%. This implies that Nigeria lagged behind in job creation. One of the primary factors was the job loss following privatization in Nigeria (Kumssa, 2000a; NBS, 2013).

According to Ogunde (2001), Nigerian experience with privatization in pursuit of a private sector economy led to retrenchment of large number of Nigerian workers. The driving force of private ownership is profits maximization; as such the immediate concern of the buyers of privatized companies was to cut down overhead costs. The Federal Government privatized its investments in petroleum, coal, electricity, water, tourism, banks, cement plants and bitumen, as workers of the attached companies lost their jobs in droves. The privatization of NICON insurance Ltd, Benue Cement Company (BCC), African Petroleum (AP), and National Oil threw able-bodied men and women into the labour market. Significantly, privatization of NITEL led to the sack of more than 7000 workers (The vanguard, 15 August 2006). Despite opening the economy through privatization and deregulation, allowing market force to determine economic trend, the employment situation in Nigerian has remained very poor. Nigeria's unemployment rate rose to 5% in the third quarter of 2023, up from 4.2% in the previous period. The jobless rate among young people aged 15-24 rose to 8.6% from 7.2%. Unemployment in the urban areas also increased marginally to 6% from 5.9% in the previous quarter (National Bureau of Statistics, 2023b).

4. ASSESSMENT OF ECONOMIC POLICY OF THE 'RENEWED HOPE' ADMINISTRATION

Nigeria is confronted with multidimensional challenges that have continued to impact on its growth and development. In this regards economic policies of the incipient government of President Tinubu will be assessed based on the economic orientation and impact on Nigeria's economic growth and development.

Fuel Subsidy Removal

In view of Nigeria's worsening debt crisis sapping on its accrued developmental revenue, the overall financial liquidity crisis and economic downturn, the government embarked on petrol subsidy removal. The removal of the petrol subsidy is a pro-market driven policy in order to achieve fiscal savings for the nation. It is anticipated that about approximately 2 trillion naira will be saved in 2023, equivalent to 0.9% of GDP. According to government, these savings are expected to reach over 11 trillion naira by the end of 2025 (Reuters 2023; NESG Special Report, 2023). However as observed, petrol subsidy removal have had a severe detrimental impact on the economy due to its negative multipliers. Prices of goods and services are on astronomic increase; the cost of transportation and energy supply for businesses which had direct consequential impact on every aspect of the nation's economic life is on the increase, with consequent rise in the nation's poverty situation (Onuah, 2023).

To tackle this trend, government under intense pressure from labour came up with palliative to cushion the effect of the subsidy removal, but arguments arises from two fronts firstly; the non-provision of adequate cushioning effect prior the policy implementation abruptly, dislocated the socioeconomic wellbeing of the masses whom, the said policy was aimed to redeem. This constricting monetary policy of government aimed at shoring up financial capital has further placed the Nigerian economy into comatose, as accumulated funds are not adequately ploughed back to stimulate the economy by way of grants to Small Medium Enterprises (SMEs), Corporations and industries, and infrastructural development to catalyze growth (NESG, 2023). There is un-sustainability of businesses due to high cost of energy, and dwindling patronage resulting from the erosion of purchasing power of the masses arising from sustained inflation. The current situation if not effectively mitigate could transcend from socioeconomic crisis to sociopolitical instability; such as political unrest, increase in crime rates and general insecurity. Secondly, there is no guarantee that fund generated from the subsidy removal if redeployed could catalyze growth as the nations still suffers from institutionalized corruption and parochial politicization of government policies and its implementation.

Liberalization of the Foreign Exchange (FX) Market

According to the government, the idea of foreign exchange (FX) management reforms is to rebuild the fiscal space and restore macroeconomic stability, engender economic growth, as well as job creation and poverty reduction. It is anticipated that the replacement of fixed exchange regime with the floating regime will increase the foreign exchange in the country and lead to a situation where dollars are sold at different prices in both the official market and the parallel market. However, it is argued that since the Nigerian economy is import dependent, this policy has resulted in high commodity prices and a fall back effect on the standard of living of Nigerian masses. The removal of fixed exchange rate led to serious volatility of the Naira against the dollar. The consequence is high cost of FOREX, which has lead to high cost of importation, with severe consequences for businesses sustainability, as goods are produce at an extreme cost. Thus to survive, business owners pass down this cost to Nigerians who are in constant struggle for a means of survival (Ifeakandu, 2023; Itsibor, Idowu and Olushola , 2023).

Also, compounding the subsidy removal is the fact that the liberalization of the foreign exchange (FX) market presents a counterproductive situation. With a floating FX regime, the NNPC (Nigerian National Petroleum Corporation) and other PMS importers now obtains dollars at a higher rate, leading to increased cost of PMS importation, thereby diminishing the accrued

monetary gains from subsidy removal. Added consequences, is pressure to further increase PMS prices, with upward effect on other prices, making the cost of living an existential concern for the populace. Analyzing the impact of eroding purchasing power on the populace showed that more Nigerians have been dragged into the poverty net. According to the World Bank's Nigeria Development Update (NDU) (2023), about 133 million Nigerians are currently living below the poverty line. The soaring inflationary pressure in 2023, added 4 million Nigerians to the existing number of people living within the poverty bracket (NESG, 2023).

Lifting Ban on Importation

The WTO free market regime that President Tinubu's regime has succumbed to in lifting ban on imported goods will further stifle what is left of the industrial sector in Nigeria. The Central Bank of Nigeria lifted the foreign exchange restrictions it placed on importers of 43 items eight years ago. Arguing, the central bank stated that this action will boost liquidity in the Nigerian Foreign Exchange Market, and that such intervention will continue from time to time, but will decrease as liquidity improves. This policy is criticized on the basis that for a nation that aim to develop its domestic economy will not pursue a liberal market policy that will stifle its domestic industrial growth potentials. As budding home industry gradually begin to fold up due to competitive disadvantage, and goods imported with high FOREX flooding the market will leave the masses in a more deplorable poverty situation, and as an import dependent nation (Okiki, 2023).

5. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

This study assessed the nexus between the private sector led economy and Nigeria economic development. In doing this, the paper provided a critique on the dynamics of the private sector led economic system and its potential to catalyze growth and socioeconomic development. The research contextualized the current government's adoption of a private sector economy via the pursuit of market rational or pro-market system approach. The study associated the intensification of Nigeria economic crisis, unemployment and poverty, and overall decline in Human Development Index to the operation of a private sector economy without adequately ensuring an effective government interventionist programmes to accommodate social safety issues especially for vulnerable groups in the society.

Findings revealed that the promised benefits of low prices and efficient services for the Nigerian masses resulting from product competitiveness of the private sector and market forces remain elusive in Nigeria. And rather than employment generation, Nigeria continues to experience job losses, high rate of unemployment, the mirage of technology transfer, and industrial stagnation, as well as poor welfare of workers. The paper argues that the private sector economy which suffers from lack of adequate government intervention mechanism especially as it affects social welfare has resulted in the widening gap of inequality and poor redistribution wealth. Thus the paper concludes that the current regime's adoption of the market driven policies will neither enhanced economic growth, or tackle poverty. Government ought to regulate and clearly set the terms of its market economy to create room for growth and inclusive development, as well as consider effective funding of social programs that aligns with public yearning e.g, education and health to the poor, while exploiting the nation private sector.

Regarding public spending, fiscal wisdom is not necessarily austerity measures; it also entails an equitable wealth redistribution and meaningful use of resources. Thus the issue is not whether government is spending money or not, the real issue is the economic utility and quality

of the expenditure. We recommend that government should implement a national industrial policy to encourage industrial sector growth and ensure that key industries begin to employ the country's growing population. As observed, foreign investors attract huge domestic capital from Nigerian banks, while profits derived from such investment is repatriated almost 100% out of the country to the benefit of the investors' home nation, with huge economic loss to Nigeria. Therefore, government should set the conditions needed to attract foreign investment and regulate the amount of capital repatriation. Government should also prioritize security as security is crucial in attracting and retaining investment, as well as retention of investment capital.

There is urgent need to improve the performance of public institutions where processes are strictly enshrined. This is in view of the fact that economic reforms are bound to be derailed without a strong and efficient institutional framework, and enforcement. With strong institutions, policies are objectively made and carried out, and the scale of political corruption is drastically reduced. For the purpose of emphasis, the current government should reconsider its fiscal and monetary policies to stabilize the Naira. Engage in massive productive spending on infrastructure, industrialization, and on medium and non-formal sector to generate economies of scale and multipliers for the economy. And also, embark on more practical, transparent, and an accountable economic empowerment programmes for inclusive growth and poverty reduction.

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